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Interplay of Oxidative Stress and Inflammatory Genes in Alzheimer's Disease Pathogenesis

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ABSTRACT

Neurodegenerative disorders (ND) are defined as a range of pathological conditions that lead to gradual and progressive neuronal loss and synapse loss in specific regions of the brain, resulting in dysfunction and irreversible changes in the central nervous system. Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is a chronic neurological condition characterised by memory loss, cognitive impairment, and behavioural disturbances that progressively worsen over time. Evidence indicates that oxidative stress and inflammation significantly contribute to the pathophysiology and development of AD. These pathogenic factors are tightly regulated at the molecular level by unique gene networks that control immunological responses, neuronal survival, and the metabolism of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Genes associated with oxidative stress involved in the pathogenesis of AD include ERF, FAR2, DDAH2, HBA2/HBA1, CYP4F12, ATP11A, PPP3CA, and TMEM70. Reduced expression levels or impaired functionality of these genes lead to ROS accumulation, causing lipid peroxidation, mitochondrial dysfunction, and neuronal damage in AD.

Furthermore, APOE4 genotypes, which are highly linked to oxidative stress in the brain, are recognised as susceptibility genes for both the pathophysiology and phenotype of AD. Unsurprisingly, neuroinflammation also plays a crucial role in the pathophysiology of AD. The six genes that are primarily responsible for inducing inflammation in AD are CR1, CLU, HLA-DRB5/DRB1, INPP5D, MEF2C, and TREM2. It has been proposed that CLU indirectly influences the production of inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6 and TNF- α . By promoting A β aggregation, regulating astrocyte and microglia-mediated A β clearance and complement activation, and inducing microglial activation, CLU appears to play a significant role in AD pathogenesis. MEF2 governs microglial proliferation, which may contribute to the inflammatory processes occurring in the cerebral tissues of AD patients.

The relationship between mRNA expression levels and protein expression for many of these genes remains unclear. Further research is necessary to determine the potential of these novel biomarkers for assessing oxidative stress, neuroinflammation, and disease status in AD patients.

Keywords:-Neuroinflammation, oxidative stress, neurodegeneration, genes, pathological conditions

INTRODUCTION

Neurodegenerative diseases (ND) are well known as a range of degenerative conditions that lead to gradual and progressive neuronal loss and synapse loss in a particular region of the brain, resulting in dysfunction and irreversible changes in the central nervous system. Some factors, including endogenous, genetic, and environmental variables linked to ageing, contribute to the initial development of ND, even though the basic molecular mechanisms underlying the disease are still unknown [1].

NDS are presently divided depending on the genetic mechanism and the nature of the component present in the protein's deposition. In ageing tissues, the accumulation of mitochondrial DNA mutations may lead to oxidative damage and the production of reactive oxygen species [1].

Amyloid- β peptides may result from the age-related generation of ROS and a reduction in adenosine triphosphate (ATP). In AD individuals, the A β peptides penetrate the mitochondria, generate free radicals, impair the function of cytochrome oxidase, and eventually hinder the production of ATP molecules. The transport of amyloid precursor protein (APP) to the outer membrane of the mitochondria in AD brains enables nuclear cytochrome oxidase proteins to be transported to the mitochondria, which may be a contributing factor to a reduction in activity of cytochrome oxidase in AD

brains. In the neurons of AD patients, amyloid β from the mitochondrial matrix attaches itself to A β -binding alcohol dehydrogenase, leading to the generation of ROS, which finally impairs mitochondrial functions. ApoE4's N-terminal sequence is linked to mitochondria, produces free radicals, and induces oxidative damage. Presenilins, anterior pharynx-defective, and nicastrin are part of the gamma secretase complex proteins found in the mitochondria, which may be involved in the synthesis of A β and the formation of free radicals [2].

ROS, which are groups of atoms with an odd, unpaired number of electrons that generate oxidative stress, significantly influence the pathophysiology of ND. This influence is further worsened by mitochondrial impairment and a reduction in the gene expression of antioxidants [3].

According to the well-established theory of free radical ageing, oxidative damage caused by ROS is a primary factor in ageing [4]. Environmental exposures like ROS can induce abnormal changes in the epigenome and modify DNA methylation in chronic disorders, potentially triggering some chronic diseases [4]. It has been identified that APOE4 genotypes, which are strongly associated with oxidative stress in the brain, are susceptibility genes for the pathophysiology and phenotype of AD [5].

The main source of highly active endogenous biological ROS, despite the presence of both external and internal

sources, is the mitochondria. In mitochondria, the electron transport chain (ETC) reduces O₂ to H₂O₂ through a four-electron process, producing superoxide anion (O₂^{•-}) and hydroxyl (•OH) radicals [6]. Unlike exogenous sources such as radiation, chemicals, and various medications [7], endogenous ROS are also made by activation of immune cells, ischaemia, inflammation, infection, too much exercise, mental stress, cancer, and ageing [8].

Enzymatic reactions, such as those produced by the electron transport chain and phagocytosis, differ from non-enzymatic ones like oxidative phosphorylation in aerobic respiration. Peroxisomes and the endoplasmic reticulum, which carry out various catabolic processes, are significant yet modest producers of ROS [8]. These potentially harmful reactive oxidative intermediates are byproducts of regular metabolic activity and can substantially contribute to the development of several neurological conditions [9]. Like actual hypoxia, pseudohypoxia caused by an increased ratio of free NADH to NAD⁺ in the cytosol can also mediate disorders of the brain and arteries. Excessive ROS formation within the mitochondria can lead to the oxidation of mitochondrial lipids, DNA, and proteins. Furthermore, it has been observed that oxidative stress is linked to protein misfolding, as demonstrated in Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease [10].

Neuronal inflammation functions as a defence mechanism that primarily shields the brain by eliminating/preventing various infections [11]. Persistent inflammatory activation may be due to endogenous factors (such as mutated genes and aggregated proteins) or environment based variables (including infection, trauma, and medication use). Chronic inflammation involving astrocytes and microglia can lead to neurological disorders [12].

Distributed evenly across the brain, microglia are the primary innate immune cells and mainly respond to pathophysiological damage [13]. Their proportion within the mouse brain varies by region, ranging from 5 to 12%. Microglia exhibit various morphologies, including compact spherical, longitudinally branching, or radially branched forms. They play three key roles in host defence and maintaining homeostasis [14]. Sensors, encoded by many genes, allow microglia to detect environmental changes in the first role. The second involves routine housekeeping tasks such as synapse remodelling, migration to injured areas, and maintaining myelin integrity. In the third, they prevent harmful catalysts like damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs) and pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) [15]. Microglial receptors, such as nuclear oligomerisation domain-like receptors, toll-like receptors (TLRs), and viral receptors, recognise PAMPs and DAMPs. In response, microglia release proinflammatory cytokines and chemokines, such as C-C motif chemokine ligand 2 (CCL2) and IL-18, to recruit additional cells and eliminate harmful substances [16].

Based on their degree of activation, the microglia in the CNS can either be pro-inflammatory or neuroprotective. Pathogens or injured cells release cytokines, which cause microglia in the resting state to release pro-inflammatory substances such as nitric oxide (NO) and proteases. These factors contribute to brain diseases [17]. These microglial components are linked to tissue repair and neuroprotection [18]. Astrocytes are the common type of glial cells present in the brain. Recent studies show that astrocytes actively participate in maintaining brain homeostasis, contradicting their earlier classification as passive support cells [19]. Astrocytes can exhibit a broad range of reactive profiles simultaneously. However,

further research is needed to understand the variability of reactive astrocytes. Like microglia, astrocytes have both pro-inflammatory and immunoregulatory subpopulations [20]. The detrimental effects of reactive astrocytes include upregulating numerous genes (such as those involved in the complement cascade) and producing pro-inflammatory molecules (IL-1 β , TNF- α , and NO) [21]. Conversely, neuroprotective reactive astrocytes upregulate thrombospondins and various neurotrophic factors [22]. The neuroprotective activation of astroglia can be triggered by anti-inflammatory cytokines like IL-4, IL-13, and IL-10. These alternatively activated astrocytes then produce TGF- β , IL-4, and IL-10 [19]. Inflammatory mediators such as TNF- α , IL-1 α , and IL-1 β , as well as C1q, are produced by pro-inflammatory microglial cells and can, in turn, trigger pro-inflammatory astroglia, leading to an inflammatory response [23]. Several other cytokines, sphingolipids (such as sphingosine 1-phosphate and LacCer), and neurotrophins can activate harmful signalling pathways in astrocytes [24]. When IL-17 binds to its receptors, pro-inflammatory cytokines may be produced, and nuclear factor κ B (NF κ B) activator 1 (Act1) could be recruited [25]. Conversely, astroglia that respond to specific pathways are neuroprotective because neuronal inflammation and cell death increase when mediators of these pathways are blocked. Glycoprotein gp130 mediates a primary protective pathway that limits neuronal inflammation and involves SHP2/Ras/ERK activation [26]. TGF β mediates a second protective pathway and has notable immunosuppressive properties. Following a stroke or Toxoplasma infection, astrocytic TGF- β signalling may reduce neuroinflammation by suppressing NF κ B signalling [27]. Interferon (IFN)- γ signalling represents a third protective pathway. Although IFN- γ is a cytokine that promotes inflammation, death and

infiltration of leukocytes in mice during the later stages of experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE) are increased when its signalling in astrocytes is blocked [28].

ROLE OF GENES ASSOCIATED WITH OXIDATIVE STRESS IN AD

A report shows that the brain of an AD patient exhibits severe oxidative damage caused by abnormal A β buildup and neurofibrillary tangle deposition [29]. Increasing evidence suggests that bio-metals such as iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), and copper (Cu²⁺) contribute to the deposition of A β and the progression of AD. These findings indicate that the N-terminal metal-binding domains of A β and its precursor (APP) possess high-affinity binding sites for Cu²⁺ and Zn [30]. The considerable presence of copper (Cu²⁺) in amyloid plaques suggests that copper strongly mediates the hydroxyl radical (OH \bullet), which leads to elevated oxidative insult, a key feature of AD [31]. The length of A β fragments appears to influence this process, as A β ₁₋₄₂ is more harmful than A β ₁₋₄₀ and is more likely to generate ROS, such as H₂O₂ [32]. Elevated zinc levels are also linked with learning, memory and behaviour (cognition) areas of the CNS, which are most affected in AD. Zinc binding causes alterations in A β ₁₋₄₀, ultimately resulting in the accumulation of detrimental fibrillary A β . Hence, the immune and inflammatory responses to insoluble A β aggregates involve oxidative stress-induced disruption of zinc homeostasis and unregulated zinc release from the brain. Therefore, excess zinc or A β deposits cause oxidative damage and neurotoxicity mediated by zinc and A β [33].

Moreover, free radical-induced oxidation of proteins may be crucial for AD since it can impact enzymes essential for neuronal and glial functioning. Glutamate synthetase and creatine kinase, two enzymes particularly susceptible to

oxidative transformation, are significantly decreased in AD brains, indicating changes in glutamate levels and increased excitotoxicity [34]. Conversely, oxidative damage to creatine kinase (CK) may reduce the metabolic energy in AD [35]. Proteins aggregate pathologically, forming fibrils and becoming insoluble [36]. Thus, the tau (τ) protein aggregates and becomes hyperphosphorylated, forming paired helical filaments, which is a characteristic of neurofibrillary tangles. Phosphorylation and oxidation are connected by the microtubule-associated protein kinase (MAPK) signalling pathway and nuclear factor- κ B transcription factor (NF- κ B) activation, which could link oxidation to τ protein hyperphosphorylation [37]. Protein oxidation can also cause advanced glycation end products, a post-translational alteration of proteins released when the amino group of proteins interacts non-enzymatically with monosaccharides [38]. Additionally, DNA can be altered by brain oxidation, leading to base modification, sister chromatid exchange (SCE), cross-linking of DNA-protein, and strand breakage [39]. Therefore, excessive ROS generation leading to oxidative damage may be detrimental and a key factor in cell structure destruction, which in turn may contribute to several disease conditions and ageing. Antioxidant therapies, however, have shown that AD is a more complicated disorder associated with oxidative stress.

In most tissues, the primary intracellular source of ROS is the electron transport chain (ETC). Different types of antioxidants defences and repair enzymes maintain oxidants at a steady, non-detrimental level. However, insufficient antioxidant defences, impaired flow of electrons, or xenobiotic exposure can damage the delicate balance between oxidants, antioxidant defences, and the formation of ROS. Such an imbalance can become a common factor in pathophysiological processes involving

oxidative damage, which further leads to the damage or death of tissue via injury. So, alterations in the redox balance of transition metals, specifically iron and copper, are important. Given the brain's susceptibility to oxidative stress, this factor is vital in the context of dementia [40]. The genes and their mechanisms to affect the pathogenesis of AD are mentioned in Table 1 in tabular form.

ERF AND TARGET GENES

The AP2/ERF superfamily, which also includes the AP2 and RAV families, includes the ERF family, an important gene family of transcription factors [41]. The AP2/ERF domain, which donates to DNA obligatory and comprises roughly 60 to 70 amino acids, establishes the AP2/ERF superfamily. The three families included are as follows. In addition to the single AP2/ERF domain, the proteins of the RAV family also have a B3 domain, a DNA-binding domain shared with other plant-specific transcript factors, such as VP1 ABI3. The proteins of the AP2 family have two recurrent AP2/ERF domains, while the proteins of the ERF family have a single AP2/ERF domain. It is occasionally feasible to further subdivide the ERF family into 2 subdivisions, including the CBF/DREB and the ERF [42]. The AP2 domain was initially exposed as a recurring pattern in the AP2 protein of Arabidopsis (*Arabidopsis thaliana*), a plant involved in the growth of flowers [43]. The ERF domain was primarily found as a conserved pattern in 4 tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*) DNA-binding proteins: ethylene-responsive element-binding proteins 1, 2, 3, and 4 (EREBP1, 2, 3, and 4, now known as ERF1, 2, 3, and 4). Regarding the RAV family, RAV1 and RAV2 were initially found to be full-length cDNAs coding for proteins in Arabidopsis that had an AP2/ERF domain and a B3-like domain [44].

Several reports demonstrate the specific contribution of ERF in the pathophysiology of AD. In comparison to normal individuals, ERF levels were markedly increased in the early stages of AD and reached a peak in mild AD [45]. The Ets-2 repressor factor protein, which is widely found across many tissues and organs, is encoded by ERF. It has been found that Ets-2 repressor factor attaches to the c-ets-2 promoter and plays a role in regulating cell proliferation, whereas the co-activator cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP)-response element binding (CREB)-binding protein/p300 has been identified as a trigger for Ets2-mediated transcription [40]. The reaction of Ets-1 to different forms of stress, such as oxidative damage, has been extensively studied. For example, it has been shown that Ets-1 responds promptly to hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) [47]; however, there is limited literature on Ets-2 under these conditions. It has been demonstrated that exposure to H₂O₂ in a 3T3 fibroblast cell line induces Ets-2 mRNA expression, which subsequently increases the cells' susceptibility to H₂O₂-mediated apoptosis [48]. Another study proving a connection between oxidative damage and Ets2 further demonstrated how oxidative stress linked to an ALS model can induce Ets-2 [49]. Numerous publications indicate the participation of gene products resulting from Ets-2-mediated transcriptional activity, despite the lack of research on the direct implication of Ets-2 in the oxidative damage response. For instance, primary cells generated from p53^{-/-} mice are resistant to H₂O₂ exposure, whereas mouse embryonic fibroblasts treated with H₂O₂ exhibit a p53 transcriptional reaction [50]. In turn, P53 is said to be crucial in controlling the amounts of ROS in cells, for example, by partially inhibiting glycolysis and increasing the synthesis of nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH) [51]. In particular, p53 levels were shown to be higher in AD

brains [52], and it was demonstrated that p53 interacted with the tau (τ) protein and Aβ in the AD brain. Parkinson-related protein α-synuclein is encoded by the SNCA gene [53], which has been linked to the production of GATA-binding factor 1, a master erythroid transcription factor. It was found that α-synuclein, more especially, aggregated α-synuclein was linked to the development of oxidative stress in the SNCA-knock-out model of mice [54].

FAR2

APO-1 or Fas receptor is a 45 kDa type I transmembrane glycoprotein belonging to the neuronal growth factor receptor or tumour necrosis factor (TNF) receptor superfamily. It comprises 335 amino acids: 16 form the putative signal sequence; 155 make up the extracellular region, which contains three cysteine-rich domains (CRD1, CRD2, and CRD3); 19 form the transmembrane region; and 145 constitute the intracellular portion, including 80 amino acids called the long "domain of death". It is vital for the physiological regulation of apoptosis, or programmed cell death. Furthermore, it has a crucial part in initiating peripheral tolerance and thymic selection within the immune system. The aetiology of several immune system disorders and cancers has been related to mutations and alterations in the APO-1/Fas gene [55].

Numerous studies have specifically examined how FAS contributes to the neurodegeneration associated with AD. According to certain theories, amyloid-β (Aβ) can directly cause neuronal death through apoptotic pathways [56]. One study reported that FAS ligand (FASL-G) overexpression and changes in FAS immunoreactivity were observed in neuronal cells in the AD individuals and Aβ-exposed cell culture [57]. It has been demonstrated that FASL-G expression was notably increased in amyloid plaques and neurofilament-positive dystrophic neurites

(NPDP). Another study revealed that transgenic mice overexpressing the wild-type human APP exhibited significantly increased FAS expression [58]. It also contributes to the progression of AD-related neuronal deterioration, as evidenced by the overexpression of FAS messenger RNA and surface receptors in peripheral T-lymphocytes of AD individuals [59], the upregulation of FAS mRNA in the AD subjects, and the significantly raised levels of FAS in the CSF of AD individuals in comparison to the healthy subjects [60]. According to a transcriptome investigation, FAR2's mRNA expression levels gradually decrease as AD worsens. [61]. Moreover, it was shown that subjects with PD, AD, and HIV-linked dementia exhibit downregulated FAR2 [62], and its role was also identified in a bioinformatic study affecting the hippocampal region in AD [63]. Although this gene has been repeatedly identified in various studies, its exact molecular mechanism in contributing to AD pathogenic processes remains unclear. The enzyme fatty acyl coenzyme A (CoA) reductase 2, encoded by the peroxisomal protein FAR2, converts 16- or 18-carbon saturated fatty acids and, to a lesser extent, shorter saturated fatty acids, into fatty alcohols. While the enzyme is mostly found in the eyelid, skin, and small intestine, the brain also shows increased levels of FAR2 mRNA [64]. It is hypothesised that FAR2-mediated activity produces cytokine precursors of transforming growth factor (TGF)- and platelet-activating factors, which act as mediators of inflammation and collectively promote mesangial matrix deposition [65]. FAR2 contributes to the stepwise production of plasmalogens, a family of glycerophospholipids with a glycerol backbone that contains sn-1-associated vinyl-ether and sn-2-associated ester [66]. Consequently, studies have found that 40 individuals with AD and cognitive decline had reduced levels of

circulating platelets in the brain [67]. Taking all this into account, various findings suggest that FAR2 may be linked to AD and the oxidative stress associated with it, possibly through an indirect pathway.

DDAH2

Dimethylarginine dimethylaminohydrolase-2 is a cytosolic protein encoded by the gene DDAH2. This enzyme participates in nitric oxide (NO) metabolism [68]. It has been shown that NO significantly influences learning and memory functions [69], and the raised oxidative stress levels found in the AD patient may be linked to DDAH2. Specifically, intracellular asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA), an endogenous blocker of nitric oxide synthase (NOS), is hydrolysed by DDAH2 [70]. Arlt et al. conducted a study involving 80 AD individuals to measure ADMA levels in plasma and CSF and compare them to those in healthy controls. The results showed significantly elevated ADMA levels in plasma and notably reduced in the CSF of AD subjects [71]. Therefore, decreased ADMA levels might enhance oxidative damage and act as a key variable in the pathogenesis of AD [72]. Recent research has also explored new biomarkers and protein co-expression in AD. Proteomic analysis revealed that DDAH2 was one of the most highly upregulated proteins involved in glucose and carbohydrate metabolism [73]. Transcriptome studies show that DDAH2 gene expression progressively increases throughout AD. It is hypothesised that increased DDAH2 gene expression compensates for decreased DDAH2 activity. These hypotheses are supported by findings that neuroblastoma cells exposed to IL-18 produced significant amounts of DDAH2 [74]. Another experiment involving human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVEC) exposed to 4-HNE (4-Hydroxynonenal) showed

increased intracellular ADMA levels, alongside decreased DDAH2 expression at both mRNA and protein levels [75]. It has been established that DDAH2 metabolises ADMA into citrulline and dimethylamine [76]. However, the belief that ADMA correlates with raised DDAH2 production conflicts with findings that DDAH2 was downregulated in rats subjected to ROS

through bile-duct ligation. The same study also indicated that the expression of DDAH and activity were blocked by exposure to superoxide ($O_2^{\bullet-}$) and H_2O_2 [77].

Fig.1:-Diagrammatic representation of genes that contribute to the inflammatory process for the pathogenesis of AD

HBA2/HBA1

The heme-scavenging protein haemoglobin (Hb) is made up of two subunits encoded by the genes HBA1 and HBA2. It has been shown that free haemoglobin damages cells through the heme component, which can catalyse lipid peroxidation [40]. Several reports suggest that AD affects haemoglobin levels. Consistent with this, a study conducted on rats demonstrated a positive resemblance between levels of haemoglobin expression and cognitive impairment [78]. Another prospective cohort analysis demonstrated that the chances of AD progression were

linked to both higher and lower Hb levels, indicating that maintaining Hb within strict threshold limits is crucial. The idea was further supported by the findings that high Hb levels and anaemia in this study were linked with a high chance of the progression of AD and a faster rate of cognitive decline [79]. A study with 12,305 subjects further corroborated the association between serum Hb and the chances of developing AD, revealing that both Hb (low and high) levels were related to a high chance of dementia. Specifically, anaemia was related to a 41% more chance of developing AD, while patients with

elevated Hb levels had a 20% increased chance of developing Alzheimer's compared to those with Hb within the normal range [80]. A report employing imaging of neurons by using immunofluorescence and confocal microscopy demonstrated that reduced expression levels of both Hb chains correlated with deposits of hyperphosphorylated τ protein in the cortex and hippocampal region in AD brains. Hb results from the blend of two different globin chains; however, without intracytoplasmic inclusions, Hb remained unchanged in neurons [81]. Abnormal iron metabolism plays a significant role in oxidative injury and neuronal cell death in AD. Iron is necessary for biological processes, but excessive intake can be detrimental [82]. An iron-containing protein called Hb interacts with $A\beta$ and is observed to colocalise with $A\beta$ plaques in post-mortem AD brains [83]. By oxidising Hb subunits, free heme can increase redox-active iron, which triggers the Fenton reaction and lipid peroxidation [84]. Hepexin is a scavenger protein that binds to heme and regulates its uptake to maintain iron homeostasis, thereby reducing heme/iron-mediated toxicity [85].

Interestingly, another in-vitro study demonstrated elevated Hb levels, which promote the aggregation of synthetic $A\beta_{1-40}$ [86]. This was also confirmed by another study showing increased Hb levels in plasma from AD individuals compared to healthy controls, with Hb linked to $A\beta$ aggregation [86]. Although the process by which Hb crosses the BBB remains unknown, scientists hypothesise that the dissipation of BBB integrity, found in primary stages of AD, may facilitate Hb infiltration into the brain [87].

CYP4F12

CYP4F12 belongs to the P450 family of cytochromes. A group of proteins known as the P450 superfamily plays a role in the

oxidative metabolic activities of substrates from different sources. The CYP4F family is particularly implicated in the ω -hydroxylation of eicosanoids [88]. It has been reported that the stimulation of the P53 pathway is responsible for the expression of CYP4F12 [89]. Numerous studies have linked oxidative stress to P53 signalling pathways. It has been shown that both neural and glial cells in the brain exhibit P450 activity [90, 91]. The initial sites of discovery of CYP4F12 included the human liver, colon, kidneys, and the small intestine, with the brain demonstrating limited expression of the protein [92]. It was demonstrated that CYP2C19, a member of the P450 family, affected brain homeostasis [93] and that CYP46A1 polymorphism increased the risk of AD by disrupting brain cholesterol homeostasis [94]. Additionally, overexpression of CYP46A1 has been shown to alleviate $A\beta$ pathologies and tau protein abnormalities, thereby improving cognitive function in an AD mouse model [95]. Although the precise role of CYP4F12 in AD has not yet been fully documented, another report indicates that the protein's mRNA levels rise as AD progresses [40].

ATP11A

Asymmetrical phospholipid distribution in the cell membrane. It is crucial for different cellular functions, is characteristic of eukaryotic membranes. Mammalian cells require ATP-powered enzymes with translocase function to regulate and develop asymmetric lipid distribution [96]. According to a transcriptome investigation, ATP11A is upregulated during the development of AD. Although no current publications discuss the relationship between ATP11A expression levels and AD development, several studies suggest an indirect connection between ATP11A expression, Calcium (Ca^{2+}) signalling, oxidative damage, and apoptosis. The protein

ATPase phospholipid transporter 11A, a class 6 P4-ATPase, is a cell membrane-localised translocase for phosphatidylserine and phosphatidylethanolamine, encoded by the gene ATP11A [97]. While the immediate effects of oxidative damage on ATP11A gene expression have not been molecularly described, oxidative stress-mediated perturbation of intracellular calcium (Ca^{2+}) homeostasis might be involved. The bidirectional interaction between calcium and ROS-mediated signalling pathways is physiologically sensible because intracellular Ca^{2+} homeostasis is governed by a redox-dependent mechanism. Elevated Ca^{2+} (intracellularly) levels are associated with raised ROS formation by triggering the activity of the respiratory chain. It has been observed that ATP11A activity is dose-dependently inhibited by heightened intracellular Ca^{2+} , most likely due to direct Ca^{2+} binding to ATP11A [97]. Proapoptotic factors, including procaspases and cytochrome c, are released following elevated Ca^{2+} levels, ultimately causing the activation of the mitochondrial permeability transition pore (mPTP). The ATP11A sequence contains two evolutionarily conserved caspase cleavage domains [98]. It has been shown that ATP11A have a crucial role in the removal of dead cells efficiently during apoptosis when mouse cells are treated with leucine-zippered human Fas ligand, which triggers caspase 3 activation. ATP11A was found to be fragmented and inactivated, losing its capacity to translocate phosphatidylserine [97]. Due to the vital role of the ATP11A-CDC50 complex in controlling a mechanosensitive Ca^{2+} channel implicated in myotube development, embryos of mice exhibit fatal defects when *Atp11a* is deleted [99, 100]. Simultaneously, certain ATP11A mutations co-expressed with CDC50A in COS cells either remain in the ER or show decreased phospholipid flippase activity [101]. Transgenic rodents with P4-ATPase

loss-of-function mutations display neurological diseases such as degeneration of axonal cells in the CNS and PNS [102]. Furthermore, missense mutations in P4-ATPases have been linked to affecting the functions of neurons and causing atrophic processes in humans [103, 104]. However, most research has focused solely on ATP8A2, other member of the P4-ATPase family. Although ATP11A functions somewhat similarly to ATP8A2, it has not yet been proven that mutations in ATP11A cause neuronal dysfunction in the same manner. Based on the pattern of tissue-specific mRNA expression, ATP11A mRNA is expressed in different areas of the CNS, implying a potential role relevant to brain function [105]. So far, ATP11A's involvement in oxidative stress has been demonstrated indirectly rather than through direct data, indicating that oxidative stress induces downstream reactions affecting ATP11A gene expression levels.

PPP3CA

According to transcriptomic analysis, incipient, low, and high stages of AD progressively show a decrease in levels of mRNA of the PPP3CA gene, which encodes the protein calcineurin A [106]. Three distinct isoforms of calcineurin A, including calcineurin 3 A, interact with calcineurin B to form a heterodimer that produces a calmodulin-regulated protein phosphatase [107]. Calcineurin A contains the catalytic site of this complex, while calcineurin B serves as the Ca^{2+} -binding regulatory subunit. It has been shown that when Ca^{2+} levels rise in T lymphocytes, calcineurin dephosphorylates the DNA-binding protein nuclear factor of activated T cells (NF-AT), prompting its relocation from the cytosol to the nucleus [108]. Patients with AD have truncated forms of calcineurin in their brains [109]. It has been proposed that calcineurin is activated by an increase in intracellular Ca^{2+} levels mediated via the N-methyl-D-aspartate

(NMDA) receptor [110]. AD has been linked to calcineurin-related signalling pathways in various cases. Notably, soluble oligomeric forms of A β are involved in the irreversible activation of calcineurin observed in neuronal injury [111]. NF-AT3 nuclear accumulation following exposure to soluble A β was found to correlate positively with calcineurin A levels in primary astrocyte or hippocampal cell cultures and tissue from the hippocampal region of an AD brain [112]. The significance of calcineurin in AD-related oxidative damage is evident through the interdependence of apoptosis, Ca²⁺ signalling events, and oxidative stress, as shown in a cardiomyocyte system where apoptosis results from increased intracellular Ca²⁺ levels [113]. An *in vitro* study using SHSY5Y cells reported that pharmacological blockage of calcineurin activity reduced APP expression, while activating calcineurin-NF-AT signalling decreased tau protein and neprilysin expression [114]. The calcineurin target, NF-AT, shows isoform-dependent differences in nuclear localisation and expression levels in the hippocampus of AD and MCI cases [115]. Additionally, the presence of calcineurin A isoforms fragments stimulates calcineurin-NF-AT pathways and suggests a role for calcineurin in regulating NF-AT levels [115]. In a mouse model of inflammatory brain injury, astrocyte activation was also linked to increased NF-AT expression; however, cytoplasmic NF-AT3 transcripts were upregulated, and ATP triggers nuclear translocation of NF-ATs by activating the purinergic P2X7 receptor, which promotes the formation of oxygen radicals [116]. Excessive formation of ROS and oxidative damage, especially the formation of 4-hydroxynonenal (HNE) products, impairs glutamate uptake by disrupting the function of the glutamate transporter GLT-1 (also known as EAAT2) [117]. The association between

EAAT2 reduction, astrocyte activation, and NF-AT-dependent transcriptional regulation—evidenced by identifying an NF-AT binding site in the human EAAT2 promoter—may explain the link between EAAT2 levels and calcineurin NF-AT signalling [118]. The calcineurin 1 (RCAN1) protein, expressed at increased levels and potentially mediating oxidative damage as shown in primary neuron cultures, further regulates the calcineurin-NF-AT signalling pathway [119].

TMEM70

According to transcriptomic analysis, TMEM70 mRNA levels are downregulated throughout the AD life cycle, but the impact is greatest during the moderate stages. The 260 amino acid (AA) transmembrane protein 70, located in the mitochondria, is encoded by three exons of this nuclear gene on chromosome 8q21.11. Originally synthesised as a 29 kDa forerunner protein [120, 121], TMEM70 is thought to be implicated in the biosynthesis of mitochondrial ATP synthase [122], particularly in the assembly of the F1 subunit or the interaction between the F1-F0 subunits. TMEM70 deficiency was first identified as causing a lack of ATP synthase activity due to mutations in the TMEM70 gene [122]. Nucleoid disorganisation and abnormally formed mitochondria [123] are traits observed in patients with such mutations. In neonatal individuals with inherited TMEM70 defects, there was an almost complete ATP synthase deficiency in the mitochondria [123]. The breakdown of the mitochondrial electron transport chain in oxidative stress is extensively studied in neurological disorders; however, in postmortem cortical brain tissue from bipolar disorder, it has been observed that, alongside oxidative damage to proteins [124], there was also a decrease in mRNA levels coding for mitochondrial complex subunits. Destruction of these genes, including complex V's ATP synthase

membrane subunit c, locus 3 (ATP5G3), which encodes the catalytic F1 subunit, has been linked to impaired expression [125]. These findings suggest that decreased TMEM70 mRNA levels, affecting the transcription of the F1-F0 subunit assembly precursor, may act as a potential marker of oxidative stress. Although no prior research has directly connected AD and TMEM70, it is noted

that an increased mitochondrial membrane potential (MMP) in response to ATP synthase activity regulation leads to reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation [126]. Based on the hypothesis that TMEM70 plays a role in ATP synthase biogenesis, Tmem70^{-/-} mice embryos demonstrated elevated SOD-2 levels without significant changes in SOD-1 levels [127].

Table 1:-Tabular form of genes contributes to the oxidative stress for the development of Alzheimer's Disease

S.No.	Gene	Mechanism of action	References
1.	ERF and target genes (Ets-2 repressor factor protein)	Ets-1 responds promptly to hydrogen peroxide, increases the cell's susceptibility to H ₂ O ₂ -mediated apoptosis, oxidative stress	47, 48
2.	FAR2	increased in amyloid plaques and neurofilament-positive dystrophic neurites, overexpression of FAS messenger RNA and surface receptors in peripheral T-lymphocytes of AD individuals	58, 59
3.	DDAH2	intracellular asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA), an endogenous blocker of nitric oxide synthase (NOS), is hydrolysed by DDAH2 into citrulline and dimethylamine, expression of DDAH and activity were blocked by exposure to superoxide (O ₂ ^{•-}) and H ₂ O ₂	70, 76, 77
4.	HBA2/HBA1	Abnormal iron metabolism plays a significant role in oxidative injury and neuronal cell death in AD, by oxidising Hb subunits, free heme can increase redox-active iron, which triggers the Fenton reaction and lipid peroxidation, elevated Hb levels, which promote the aggregation of	82, 84, 86

		synthetic A β_{1-40}	
5.	CYP4F12	stimulation of the P53 pathway is responsible for the expression of CYP4F12, p53 has been found to regulate the steady-state levels of intracellular oxidants in conjunction with p66Shc, a protein that triggers apoptosis in response to oxidative signals	90, 91
6.	ATP11A	oxidative stress-mediated perturbation of intracellular calcium (Ca ²⁺) homeostasis, Elevated Ca ²⁺ (intracellularly) levels are associated with raised ROS formation by triggering the activity of the respiratory chain, Proapoptotic factors, including procaspases and cytochrome c, are released following elevated Ca ²⁺ levels, ultimately causing the activation of the mitochondrial permeability transition pore (mPTP).	97
7.	PPP3CA	PPP3CA gene, encodes the protein calcineurin A, soluble oligomeric forms of A β are involved in the irreversible activation of calcineurin observed in neuronal injury, blockage of calcineurin activity reduced APP expression, while activating calcineurin-NF-AT signalling decreased tau protein and neprilysin expression, calcineurin 1 (RCAN1) protein, expressed at increased levels and potentially mediating oxidative damage as shown in primary neuron cultures, further regulates the calcineurin-NF-AT signalling pathway	106, 114, 115, 117

ROLE OF GENES ASSOCIATED WITH INFLAMMATION IN AD

Since 1987, more than 20 years have been spent searching for the genes linked to AD [128]. It did not produce any noteworthy outcomes until the emergence of GWAS, which transformed genetics research. GWAS is currently a widely used method for analysing genetic variants throughout the genome using single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) arrays to investigate their potential link to AD [129]. In addition to genotyping large populations (more than 1000 subjects), it can objectively identify potential genes and analyse over a million SNPs in a single subject [130]. APOE was identified as the primary genetic factor responsible for late-onset AD (LOAD) in 2009 by the first reproducible GWAS. Since then, at least nine new risk loci—ABCA7, BIN1, CR1, CD33, CD2AP, CLU, EPHA1, MS4A6A, and PICALM—have been identified through European and global genome-wide association consortia [131, 132]. CASS4, CELF1, FERMT2, HLA-DRB5/DRB1, INPP5D, MEF2C, NME8, PTK2B, SLC24A4/RIN3, SORL1, and ZCWPW1 are among the eleven novel AD risk genes recently discovered by the International Genomics of Alzheimer's Project employing a meta-analysis. Eight of the nine previously identified AD-associated genes were also confirmed (**Table 2**), including CR1, BIN1, CD2AP, EPHA1, CLU, MS4A6A, PICALM, and ABCA7; CD33 was excluded since it failed to replicate [133]. Using exome sequencing, two separate investigations simultaneously identified TREM2 as a rare but significantly contributing factor for the development of AD [134]. Unsurprisingly, various of these AD risk markers are implicated in inflammatory and immunological processes [135]. These six genes are primarily responsible for the induction of inflammation in AD: CR1,

CLU, HLA-DRB5/DRB1, INPP5D, MEF2C, and TREM2 (**Figure 1**).

Complement Receptor 1

The complement components C3b and C4b in their active forms bind to complement receptor 1 (CR1), also known as CD35. The CR1 gene is expressed on chromosome 1 at the 1q32 locus, which is part of a gene group related to complement activation [136]. The multifunctional CR1 protein is widely found on the cell membranes of B-lymphocytes, macrophages, monocytes, eosinophils, erythrocytes, dendritic cells, glomerular podocytes, certain CD4-positive T cells, and microglia [137]. There are 2 isoforms of CR1 includes CR1-F and CR1-S. The "fast" isoform, with a lower molecular weight, is indicated by the letter F, while the "slow" isoform is indicated by S [138]. In individuals with AD, CR1-S expression is less than CR1-F expression compared to healthy individuals [139]. By inhibiting complement activation through two mechanisms, CR1 reduces tissue damage and suppresses the immune response. Because CR1 regulates complement activity by functioning as a binding site of the complement C3b protein, it was hypothesised to represent a crucial component in AD pathogenesis [140]. First, CR1 reversibly attaches to C3b and C4b, inactivating complexes that include these components as well as the C3 and C5 convertases. Second, CR1 facilitates the segregation of catalytic subunits C2a or Bb, accelerating the degradation of C3 convertase [141]. The precise role of CR1-mediated complement regulation in the development of AD in the brain remains unknown. However, it is hypothesised that CR1 may aid in AD by preventing inflammation-induced neuronal damage and/or by clearing A β aggregates from the brain through C3b. Several theories have been proposed, including the lack of C3b-mediated removal of neurotoxic

aggregation of A β and the protective function of CR1 in reducing inflammation-related neuronal damage [138, 142].

Amyloid plaque removal is facilitated by CR1-mediated phagocytosis, which is crucial to the neuropathology of AD [143]. It has been demonstrated that A β activates the complement system by binding to CR1 through C1q. Increased CR1 was linked with more activated microglia, and inhibiting CR1 hindered the microglia's capacity to phagocytose A β [137]. Another study showed that the CR1 protein was linked to the A β 42 peptide at its C3b ligation region, which caused A β to be cleared [144] and affected the aggregation of A β 42 peptide in AD [145]. Therefore, CR1 is important for the clearance of amyloid plaques and is involved in the pathogenesis of AD. Additionally, it is linked to the pathogenesis of AD by regulating peripheral erythrocytes to detect circulating A β , and CR1 SNPs raise the risk of AD by altering the expression of CR1 in erythrocytes [146].

In order to better understand the genetic mechanism of sporadic AD (SAD), a meta-analysis conducted in 2020 showed a correlation between the CR1 SNP rs6656401A/G or rs3818361T/C and SAD risk in Caucasians. Additionally, it was discovered that a T carrier of rs3818361T/C or a carrier of rs6656401A/G in the CR1 genetic polymorphism may be a risk factor for SAD in Caucasians [147].

Clusterin

A multifunctional glycoprotein, clusterin (CLU), also known as apolipoprotein J, was first identified for its ability to induce cell aggregation *in vitro* [148]. There is widespread expression of CLU mRNA, and the mature CLU protein is secreted from cells to act as an extracellular chaperone. CLU is a 75–80 kDa heterodimeric protein that is highly glycosylated and stabilised by five disulfide bonds [149]. Various biological

processes, such as sperm maturation, complement-mediated cell lysis, lipid transport, and apoptosis, have been linked to CLU [150]. The association between AD and CLU has been firmly established. When comparing AD-affected brain regions to controls, it was first observed that CLU expression was significantly higher in the former. Notably, CLU, a chaperone protein, has been shown to bind A β peptides, an interaction that is crucial for A β toxicity, clearance, and aggregation [153, 154]. Furthermore, multiple studies suggest that CLU may modulate inflammation within AD pathology. In addition to its role in complement-mediated cell lysis, CLU also contributes to complement activation [155]. Its involvement in astrocyte and microglia-mediated A β clearance was recently described [156]. Moreover, it has been proposed that CLU indirectly influences the generation of inflammatory cytokines [157]. Therefore, by promoting the deposition of A β , regulating astrocyte and microglia-mediated A β clearance and complement activation, and inducing microglial stimulation, CLU have a significant participation in the pathophysiology of AD.

HLA-DRB5/DRB1

The major histocompatibility complex (MHC) proteins are encoded by the human leukocyte antigen (HLA) region, located on chromosome 6p21.3. In humans, MHC is also known as HLA. The literature frequently uses HLA and MHC interchangeably [158]. In immune responses, the proteins encoded by HLA are essential for self-recognition by immune cells, as well as antigen processing and presentation. This region includes genes involved in various processes, like histocompatibility, the complement cascade, inflammation, and ligands for immune cell receptors. The MHC complex is divided into three subdivisions: I, II, and III. Class II MHC,

situated at the centromeric end, encodes genes such as HLA-DRA, DRB1, DRB3, DRB4, DRB5, DQA1, DQB1, DPA1, and DPB1. Antigen-presenting cells like microglial cells in the brain express the class II HLA-DR antigens, which can bind to T cell receptors. Reports indicate that the substantia nigra in PD individuals and rodents with MPTP-induced Parkinsonism contains HLA-DR-positive activated microglia [159]. Since AD is another significant neurodegenerative disorder, it is reasonable to suggest that the localisation of HLA-DR in AD is likely similar to that in PD, although there is very limited experimental evidence regarding its association with AD [160].

INPP5D

INPP5D is a member of the inositol polyphosphate-5-phosphatase (INPP5) family, which is more commonly known as SHIP (also known as SHIP1 or SHIP1a), an inositol-50-phosphatase with an SH2 domain. PI-3,4-bisphosphate (PI(3,4)P₂) is formed by hydrolysing the 50-phosphate of phosphatidylinositol (PI)-3,4,5-triphosphate (PI(3,4,5)P₃) by the human SHIP protein, which is encoded by the INPP5D gene found on chromosome 2q37.1 [161]. Cells in the haematopoietic compartment are the main source of SHIP expression [162]. Regarding SHIP's biological roles, it was found to be the primary inhibitor of IgE. Levels of Ag-generated PI(3,4,5)P₃ in mast cells collected from mouse bone marrow [163]. Additionally, SHIP inhibits B cell activation, chemotaxis, and proliferation as well as the release of inflammatory cytokines from mast cells triggered by IgE or IgE-antigen (Ag) [164]. It is yet unclear how SHIP affects inflammation and immunological response in the brain. Nonetheless, based on what is currently known about SHIP, it may be able to inhibit the production of several inflammatory cytokines from neurons, astrocytes, or microglia.

MEF2C

Myocyte enhancer factor-2 (MEF2) proteins belong to the transcription factor family known as MADS (MCM1, agamous, deficient, serum response factor) [165]. In mammals, the genes encoding MEF2 proteins are MEF2A, B, C, and D. In both embryonic and adult tissues, the four MEF2 isoforms show distinct yet overlapping expression patterns. MEF2C is expressed more extensively and plays a role in various transcriptional processes, including tissue development and differentiation [166]. Furthermore, MEF2C is abundantly expressed in lymph node and splenic B cells and is crucial for B cell proliferation following antigen stimulation [167]. Recent research indicates that MEF2 is a key transcriptional element in the innate immune response of adult flies [168, 169]. Consequently, it is hypothesised that MEF2 regulates microglial proliferation, which may be implicated in the inflammatory processes occurring in the cerebral tissues of AD patients [170].

TREM2

Triggering receptor shows on myeloid cells 2 (TREM2) is an important part of the TREM group of innate immune receptors, which are believed to trigger the substitution of R47H, consequently increasing sensitivity to LOAD by three times. A 26-kDa transmembrane glycoprotein with an extracellular immunoglobulin-like site, a transmembrane domain, and a brief cytoplasmic tail is encoded by the TREM2 gene, which is found on chromosome 6p21.1 [171]. The brain's activated macrophages, osteoclasts, immature dendritic cells, and microglia also express the innate immune receptor across their extracellular membranes. It carries out its signalling activity through its association with the TYRO protein tyrosine kinase binding protein (TYROBP, also called DAP12) to produce an intricate structure

[172]. Immune responses, phagocytic activity in microglia, and the proliferation of dendritic cells and osteoclasts are all believed to be regulated by the TREM2/TYROBP complex [173]. TREM2 has been shown to inversely control inflammatory responses in the CNS by suppressing the synthesis and release of cytokines in response to the TLR2 and TLR4 ligands zymosan and LPS [174]. TREM2 is therefore thought to be advantageous in the pathophysiology of AD; its anti-inflammatory effects may lessen inflammation-induced damage to benign mediator nerve cells [175]. Furthermore, TREM2 is known to have a

role in the control of phagocytosis, which destroys damaged or apoptotic neurons, and facilitates healing in tissues in response to pathologies associated with AD [176]. A chronic neurological condition called Nasu-Hakola disease is likely to occur among individuals with a mutation that causes loss of function of TREM2, most likely because of a failure to remove tissue debris [177]. Remarkably, it has been shown that AD mice have elevated TREM2, which may be a result of their inadequate compensatory attempt to control the inflammatory response [178, 179].

Table 2:-Tabular form of genes contributes to the inflammatory process for the development of Alzheimer's Disease

S.No.	Gene	Mechanism of action	References
1.	Complement Receptor 1 (CR1)	altering CR1 expressions in erythrocytes, removal of amyloid plaque by CR1-mediated phagocytosis, aggregation of A β ₄₂ peptide	143, 145, 146
2.	Clusterin	promoting A β aggregation, regulating astrocyte and microglia-mediated A β clearance and complement activation, and inducing microglial stimulation	155-157
3.	HLA-DRB5/DRB1	localisation of HLA-DR	160
4.	INPP5D (SHIP)	inhibits B cell activation, chemotaxis, and proliferation as well as the release of inflammatory cytokines from mast cells triggered by IgE or IgE-antigen	164
5.	MEF2C	regulates microglial proliferation, which implicated in the inflammatory processes	170
6.	TREM2	lessen inflammation-induced damage, control of phagocytosis, which destroys damaged or apoptotic neurons and facilitates healing in tissues in response to pathologies associated with AD	173

CONCLUSION

AD is a chronic neurological condition characterised by loss of memory, impairment in cognition, and behavioural alteration that progressively worsens over time. Evidence shows that oxidative stress and inflammation make a significant contribution to the pathophysiology and development of AD. These pathogenic

factors are precisely regulated at the molecular level by unique gene networks that oversee immunological responses, neuronal survival, and the metabolism of ROS. Genes linked to oxidative stress implicated in the development of AD include ERF, FAR2, DDAH2, HBA2/HBA1, CYP4F12, ATP11A, PPP3CA, and TMEM70. Reduced

expression levels or impaired functioning of these genes lead to ROS accumulation, leads to mitochondrial dysfunction, and neuronal damage in AD.

Overproduction of ROS in mitochondria, as found in AD, can damage the brain's proteins and lipids. Despite research, the cellular mechanisms regulating and modulating the levels of oxidative stress in AD remain unknown. Identifying more biomarkers could offer additional insights into the molecular mechanisms and lead to the development of novel oxidative stress markers that are more specific to early-stage AD. Some genes have been found to directly influence oxidative stress regulation, while others have received less scrutiny. The relationship between mRNA expression levels and protein levels for several of these genes is also unclear.

Although considerable evidence suggests that inflammatory processes are the primary cause of the pathophysiology of AD and that reducing inflammation may be favourable, caution is necessary when considering that inflammation can be a potential target to halt or slow the progression of disorder. Strong evidence indicates that many inflammatory substances have dual roles, and their reduction could potentially exacerbate the condition. Despite the complexity of AD pathogenesis, the inflammatory pathway remains a viable target for therapeutic intervention. Advances in genetic research have improved our understanding of AD causes. Following the discovery of hundreds of risk genes in recent years, GWAS has become the prevalent approach for the detection of new AD genes. Some recently identified genes provide further insights into the role of inflammation in AD. Although it is still unclear how these genes (CR1, CLU, HLA-DRB5/DRB1, INPP5D, MEF2C, and TREM2) influence inflammation in AD, these findings enhance our understanding of the disease and could

serve as valuable therapeutic targets to improve prevention and treatment.

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